

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN ENHANCING WORK EFFECTIVENESS OF AN ORGANIZATION

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Annotatsiya: Muloqot asosiy hayotiy dastaklardan biridir kompaniya guruhlarini tartibga solish uchun bajarishi mumkin bo'lgan boshqaruv va foydali bajarilishini ta'minlash. Aloqa va ma'muriyat bir-birini to'ldiruvchi fanlar va mustahkam tijoratdir g'alaba uchun komponentlar. Ma'muriy qobiliyatlar kasbda asosiy hisoblanadi, Lekin shunga o'xshash hayotiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lganlarning barchasi qoidalar bilan bog'liq aloqa va nazoratchi qanday qilishni bilishi xodimlari bilan bog'langan. Nazoratchi bo'lish bu jilovlash degani emas tijorat, lekin odatda guruhni, ma'muriyatni tashkil qilishni bilishni nazarda tutadi qobiliyat va eng muhimi, muloqot.

Kalit so`zlar: savdo aloqasi, tashkiliy aloqa, ish samaradorligi

Abstract: Communication is one of the foremost vital levers of administration that a company can execute for the arrangement of groups and accomplishing profitable execution. Communication and administration are complementary disciplines and solid commerce components for victory. Administration aptitudes are basic in a trade, but all similarly vital are those relating to the rules for the communication

and the way in which a supervisor knows how to connected with his staff. Being supervisor not as it were implies to curb in commerce, but generally implies knowing to arrange a group, administration aptitudes and most of all, communicate.

Key words: trade communication, organizational communication, work efficiency

Аннотация: Общение – один из основных инструментов жизни управление, которое компания может осуществлять для регулирования групп и обеспечить выгодную производительность. Коммуникация и администрация дополняют друг друга дисциплины и надежная коммерция компоненты для победы. Административные навыки являются ключевыми в профессии, Но все те, кто имеет такое жизненно важное значение, связаны правилами коммуникабельность и мастерство руководителя связаны с работниками. Быть надзирателем не значит быть сдержанным коммерческий, но обычно включает в себя умение организовать группу, администрирование умение и самое главное общение.

Ключевые слова: коммерческая коммуникация, организационная коммуникация, Эффективность работы

It is basic that any sort of organization, which wishes to seek after an action in full agreement with the society in which it exists, to start the work based on a pre-set arrange, a administration methodology carefully planned as administration speaks to a imperative angle of the working of the organizational and the social frameworks, particularly within the conditions of present day period, stamped by the expanding complexity of innovative and educational items, radical change at the level of social structure, patterns of globalization of the economy and,

particularly, changes to the item at the organizational level. In this setting we consider essential the intercession of administrative structures that will adjust to all organization changes.

2. Internal Corporate Communication Prepare Administration should consider to begin with individuals. The most point of their association within the errands they have attempted, the proficiency with which they are carried out because it may be an exceptionally imperative parameter, bearing particularly in intellect that it requires administration to work together in groups. Administration bargains with the coordination of their exercises, arranging, organization and coordination of pre-established goals,

All these components shape the premise of communication forms, whereby people of an organization will be able to set up interpersonal associations, which are the premise of great administration exercises, both inside and remotely. more frequently such variables of non-financial inspiration.

Inner proficient communication has been challenged over the final decade, slowly passing from the inside communication programs planning only for the dispersal of data inside the organization, whether uni-or bi-directional, to programs of inclusion and inspiration of representatives (Mill operator, 2012). In common terms, communication interior a company: – makes work fulfillment: organizations that energize a dispersion of data between seniors and subordinates, as well as between workers of the same divisions; a great criticism brings as it were benefits, propels representatives to work superior and makes them feel profitable to the company; open communication avoids the event of clashes and makes a difference tackling them speedier. When a struggle is settled through dialog, workers create shared regard, which leads to an

their advancement, both professionally and actually; – develops efficiency; compelling communication within the working environment is a critical issue for the victory or disappointment of the organization; supervisors got to characterize, to clarify altogether the destinations to be fulfilled, communicate to workers the responsibilities and obligations that ought to be met; in case the line ahead is evident, the representatives will know precisely what they need to do and how to focus on that, driving to expanded efficiency; – employments assets more viably: when issues, emergencies and clashes emerge in an organization, due to the need of communication between representatives, superfluous delays within the every day schedule happen; it comes down to a asset spill and conclusion up in diminishing the in general efficiency.

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